

Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPTool

Title: DMP - Recommendations and tips (DCC Template)

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DMP - Recommendations and tips (DCC Template)

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

Every component of the DMP depends upon knowing how much and what types of data will be collected. Data volume is clearly important, as it normally costs more to manage 10 terabytes of data than 10 megabytes, both in terms of infrastructure and personnel. But other data attributes also affect costs, metadata, quality assurance, and preservation strategies, and even data policies. A good plan will include information that is sufficient to understand the nature of the data that is collected, including:

Types. A good first step is to list the various data types you expect to collect, compile or create. This may include text, spreadsheets, software and algorithms, models, images and movies, audio files, and patient records. Many research sponsors define data broadly, including physical collections, software and code, and curriculum materials. **Sources.** Data may come from direct human observation, laboratory and field instruments, experiments, simulations, and compilations of data from other studies. Reviewers and sponsors may be particularly interested in understanding if data are proprietary, are being compiled from other studies, pertain to human subjects, or are otherwise subject to restrictions in their use or redistribution.

Tips: Describe and cite your secondary data sources. Take notes about their limitations and provenance. Are there any licensing restrictions on third-party data you are re-using?

See:

- [Data Citation in a Nutshell](#)
- [Persistent Identifiers Explained](#)
- [Know Your Rights & Use Data Right!](#)

Volume. Outline the total volume of data and the total number of files expected to be collected can affect all other data management activities (storage, backup, access, preservation, etc.) Giving the hosting institution a heads-up about the anticipated infrastructure to manage large volumes of data is important.

- Note what volume of data you will create in MB/GB/TB. Indicate the proportions of raw data, processed data, and other secondary outputs (e.g., reports).
- Consider the implications of data volumes regarding storage, access, and preservation. Do you need to include additional costs?
- Consider whether the scale of the data will pose challenges when sharing or transferring data between sites; if so, how will you address these challenges?

See:

- [Compressing files](#)

Data and file formats. Technology changes and formats that are acceptable today may soon be obsolete. Good choices include those formats that are nonproprietary, based upon open standards, and widely adopted and preferred by the scientific community (e.g., Comma Separated Values [CSV] over Excel [.xls, .xlsx]). Data are more likely to be accessible for the long term if they are uncompressed, unencrypted, and stored using standard character encodings such as UTF-16.

Tips:

- Explain why you have chosen certain formats. Decisions may be based on staff expertise, a preference for open formats, the standards accepted by data centers, or widespread usage within a given community.
- Using standardized, interchangeable, or open formats ensures the long-term usability of data; these are recommended for sharing and archiving.

See:

- DataONE Best Practices for [file formats](#)
- [Why do open formats matter?](#)

How will the data be collected or created?

Once there is an understanding of the volume and types of data to be collected, the next obvious step is to define how the data will be organized and managed. For many projects, a small number of data tables will be generated that can be effectively managed with commercial or open-source spreadsheets programs like Excel and OpenOffice Calc. Larger data volumes and usage constraints may require using relational database management systems (RDBMS) for linked data tables like ORACLE or MySQL, or a Geographic Information System (GIS) for geospatial data layers like ArcGIS, GRASS, or QGIS.

The details about how the data will be organized and managed could fill many pages of text and, in fact, should be recorded as the project evolves. However, in drafting a DMP, it is most helpful to initially focus on the types and, possibly, names of the products used. The software tools employed in a project should be amenable to the anticipated tasks. A spreadsheet program, for example, would be insufficient for a project in which terabytes of data are expected to be generated, and a sophisticated RDBMS may be overkill for a project in which only a few small data tables will be created. Furthermore, projects dependent upon a GIS or RDBMS may entail considerable software costs and design and programming effort that should be planned and budgeted for upfront.

Depending on sponsor requirements and space constraints, it may also be useful to specify conventions for file naming, persistent unique identifiers (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers [DOIs]), and versioning control (for both software and data products).

See:

- [How can research data be reused?](#)
- [The Dos and Don'ts of File Naming](#)
- [Persistent Identifiers Explained](#)
- [Take full control of file versions!](#)
- [DataONE - Data Quality Control and Assurance](#)

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Explain how the data and associated code will be documented.

Rows and columns of numbers and characters have little to no meaning unless they are documented in some fashion. Metadata—the details about what, where, when, why, and how the data were collected, processed, and interpreted—provide the information that enables data and files to be discovered, used, and properly cited. Metadata include descriptions of how data and files are named, physically structured, and stored and details about the experiments, analytical methods, and research context. It is generally the case that the utility and longevity of data relate directly to how complete and comprehensive the metadata are. The amount of effort devoted to creating comprehensive metadata may vary substantially based on the data's complexity, types, and volume.

A sound documentation strategy can be based on three steps:

- 1) Identify the types of information that should be captured to enable any researcher (including your future self) to discover, access, interpret, use, and cite your data.
- 2) Determine whether a community-based metadata schema or standard (i.e., preferred sets of metadata elements) can be adopted. In many cases, a specific metadata content standard will be recommended by a target data repository, archive, or domain professional organization.
- 3) Identify software tools that can be employed to create and manage metadata content (e.g., Metavist, Morpho, R Packages). In lieu of existing tools, text files (e.g., readme.txt) that include the relevant metadata can be included as headers for the data files.

A best practice is to designate a data manager responsible for maintaining an electronic lab notebook, in which all project details and documentation are represented. The notebook should ideally be routinely reviewed and revised by another team member and duplicated. The metadata recorded in the notebook provide the basis for the metadata associated with data products to be stored, reused, and shared.

Tips:

Consider clients' needs, which standards are supported by the repositories you plan to upload the data, and always give preference to metadata standards widely adopted in your research community (this is key for interoperability). When in doubt:

- What metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data?
- Researchers are strongly encouraged to use community metadata standards where these are in place. Data repositories may also provide guidance about appropriate metadata standards.
- Consider what other documentation is needed to enable reuse. This may include information on the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, units of measurement, any assumptions made, the format and file type of the data and software used to collect and/or process the data.
- Consider how you will capture this information and where it will be recorded, e.g., in a database with links to each item, in a 'readme' text file, in file headers, etc.
- Document as you progress, do not wait until the end of the project, otherwise it will take more time, and chances are some details won't be as well-represented/captured.

Sources:

- [RDA Metadata Standard Directory \(EES\)](#)
- [What should you keep in your project folder?](#)
- [Championing Code Documentation](#)
- [README, please!](#)

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

Research sponsors, institutions that host research, and scientists all have a role in and obligation to promote responsible and ethical behavior. Many research sponsors require that investigators engaged in human subject research approaches seek or receive prior approval from the appropriate Institutional Review Board before a grant proposal is submitted and, certainly, receive approval before the actual research is undertaken. Approvals may require that informed consent be granted, that data are anonymized, or that use is restricted in some fashion.

Consequently, many research sponsors require that DMPs include explicit policy statements about how data will be managed and shared. Such policies include

legal and ethical restrictions on access and use of human subjects and other sensitive data concerning protected species and research sites. Proceed with caution when acquiring secondary data sources since some might not have removed indirect identifiers that can still compromise privacy and anonymity. If your project involves any sensitive data, your DMP should address ways to mitigate those issues, including:

- Have you gained consent for data preservation and sharing?
- How will you protect the identity of participants if required? e.g., via anonymization
- How will sensitive data be handled to ensure it is stored and transferred securely?

See:

- [The Spectrum of Human Subjects' Privacy](#)
- [CARE Principles](#)
- [Identify Data Sensitivity](#)

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IP/IPR) issues?

Explain how and when the data and other research products will be made available. Explain any embargo periods or delays, such as publication or patent reasons. A common practice is making data broadly available at the time of publication or, in the case of graduate students, when the graduate degree is awarded.

Whenever possible, apply standard rights waivers or licenses, such as those established by Open Data Commons (ODC) and Creative Commons (CC), that guide subsequent use of data and other intellectual products (see <http://creativecommons.org/> and <http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/pddl/summary/>).

The CC0 license and the ODC Public Domain Dedication and License, for example, promote unrestricted sharing and data use. Nonstandard licenses and waivers can be a significant barrier to reuse.

See:

- [Know Your Rights & Use Data Right!](#)

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

A common mistake of inexperienced (and even many experienced) researchers is to assume that their personal computers and websites will live forever. They fail to routinely duplicate their data during the course of the project and do not see the benefit of archiving data in a secure location for the long term.

Inevitably, papers get lost, hard disks crash, URLs break, and tapes and other media degrade, resulting in the data becoming unavailable for use by both the originators and others. Thus, data storage and preservation are central to any good data management plan.

Develop a sound plan for storing and protecting data over the project's life. A good approach is to store at least three copies in at least two geographically distributed locations (e.g., original location such as a desktop computer, an external hard drive, and one or more remote sites) and to adopt a regular schedule for duplicating the data (i.e., backup). Remote locations may include an offsite collaborator's laboratory, an institutional repository (e.g., your departmental, university, or organization's repository if located in a different building), or a commercial service, such as those offered by Amazon, Dropbox, Google, and Microsoft. The backup schedule should also include testing to ensure that stored data files can be retrieved.

See:

- [DataONE - Backup](#)
- [DataONE - Storage](#)
- [Backup your data!](#)
- [Cloud Services at UCSB!](#)

How will you manage access and security?

This is especially important for projects dealing with any sensitive or restricted data. Ensure to address any access restrictions keeping in mind your client's and served community's best interests regarding data protection and security. Address plans to transfer data safely among team members.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The answer to this question depends on several factors. First, determine whether the research sponsor or your home institution has specific requirements. Usually, all data need not be retained, and those that do need not be retained forever. Follow the principle as open as possible, as restricted as needed.

A recurrent question we get: Should I share the raw data if I am re-using a publicly available data source? The answer is: It depends! If the data source is housed in a repository with a DOI, a citation and attribution on the README will suffice. In that case, you may only share derived datasets (in case you aggregate other data sources or perform transformations). However, if the dataset is on a website or ftp chances are that they won't be accessible for long-term, and we recommend you also add the raw data to the data folder of your project directory that you plan to share.

- DataONE - [Decide what data to preserve](#)

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

Researchers should consider the following goals and benefits of preservation:

- Enabling re-analysis of the same products to determine whether the same conclusions are reached
- Enabling re-use of the products for new analysis and discovery
- Enabling restoration of original products in the case that working datasets are lost

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

The best-laid preservation plans do not necessarily mean that all project data will see the light of day. Reviewers and research sponsors will be reassured that this will not be the case if you have spelled out how and when the data products will be disseminated to others, especially people outside your research group.

Funding agencies and research institutions favor more active approaches, include: (1) publishing the data in an open repository or archive; (2) submitting the data (or subsets thereof) as appendices or supplements to journal articles; and (3) publishing the data, metadata, and relevant code as a “data paper”.

A good dissemination plan includes a few concise statements. State when, how, and what data products will be made available. Generally, making data available to the greatest extent and with the fewest possible restrictions at publication or project completion is encouraged. The more proactive approaches described above are greatly preferred over mailing or emailing data and will likely save significant time and money in the long run, as the appropriate journals and repositories or archives will support the data curation and sharing.

Furthermore, many journals and repositories provide guidelines and mechanisms for how others can appropriately cite your data, including digital object identifiers (e.g., DOIs), and recommended citation formats; this helps ensure that you receive credit for the data products you create. Keep in mind that the data will be more usable and interpretable by you and others if disseminated using standards and nonproprietary approaches and if the data are accompanied by metadata and associated code used for data processing.

If available, we recommend a certified curated disciplinary data repository as your first option. If not, choose an institutional, general, or multidisciplinary repository to house your data and code.

Note on GitHub: GitHub works great for ongoing projects, but it is not a preservation tool nor one that facilitates discoverability (most repositories are now indexed on Google Data Sets). Also, Microsoft owns GitHub and does not include tracks citations and other metrics. It is also not ideal for housing projects with a combination of public and restricted datasets and no option for data user agreements if needed.

See:

- [Choosing a Data Repository](#)
- [Meet Dryad!](#)
- [RE3data.org \(Registry of Research Data Repositories\)](#)

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Again, keep data as open as possible and as protected as needed. You may need to pose some access restrictions to all or some of the datasets your project has produced.

A Data Use Agreement (DUA) is a contractual document used to transfer data developed by nonprofit, government or private industry, where the data is nonpublic or is otherwise subject to some restrictions on its use.

Be explicit about any anticipated restrictions with a compelling justification.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Clearly define the roles and responsibilities for:

- Data Creation/Capture
- Metadata and Documentation
- Ethics & Compliance
- Storage, Backup, & Encryption (if any)
- Preservation, Archiving, & Sharing

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

What institutional and external support will you need to implement your data management plan? How may that impact your budget? Some funding agencies include data management activities under allowable costs for budgets for proposals, including:

- Curating data and developing supporting documentation
- Local data management considerations
- Preserving and sharing data through established repositories

See:

- [DataONE - Budget Information for DMPs](#)
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Planned Research Outputs

Guideline - "DMP Recommendations and tips (DCC Template)"

Planned research output details

Title	Type	Anticipated release date	Initial access level	Intended repository(ies)	Anticipated file size	License	Metadata standard(s)	May contain sensitive data?	May contain PII?
DMP Recommendations and tips (DCC Template)	Guideline	2023-01-23	Open	Zenodo		Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal	None specified	No	No